

THE IMPACT OF HISTORICAL AND CURRENT EXPERIENCES OF OPPRESSION ON
BLACK MENTAL HEALTH

by

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ABSTRACT

This project investigates the historical impact of the Middle Passage, slavery, Reconstruction, the Black Codes, and the Civil Rights movement on Black Americans' current mental health struggles and racism in mental health care. An in-depth comparison of first- and second-hand historical accounts of Black Americans, as well as contemporary accounts, books, and studies about Black mental health in the present, reveal an ongoing experience of trauma from which African Americans have not been allowed to recover collectively due to unyielding racism. It also shows how Black Americans have always found psychological and emotional strength through community and music. These findings demonstrate the importance of enabling Black Americans to heal, an opportunity that is once again being denied by the United States through powerful interests attempting to ban the accurate teaching of history.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout United States history, many tragic events have happened at the expense of African Americans, such as the horrors of the Middle Passage, the brutality of enslavement, the White southern backlash against Reconstruction, living in the Jim Crow South, and physical attacks that came with participation in the Civil Rights movement. This project investigates how these events have echoed throughout history through the lens of mental health. According to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, mental health includes “emotional, psychological, and social well-being” (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services). Through this definition, the destruction or weakening of one’s mental health can also mean the destruction of one’s emotional, psychological, and social well-being. Inversely, something that strengthens this for Black people will be considered healing, and community can often be a strengthening force (Stokes et al., 2020). It makes sense that for Black people, continued exposure to racism and seeing people in their communities can harm their mental health, as showcased by the witnesses of George Floyd’s murder. A year after that event, some of the witnesses, especially the Black witnesses who also testified at the trial of Derek Chauvin, were experiencing sleep disturbances, reliving the event, and experiencing survivor’s guilt (NBC News, 2021). There is literature showing how trauma experienced by one person can affect their descendants, especially when it comes to Holocaust victims, even changing their genetics (DeGruy, 2017). How has generational trauma and other mental health effects among African Americans echoed throughout the years, and how does the continued discrimination that Black Americans face today compound that?

METHODOLOGY

The primary approach used was historical research design, aiming to look at past events to understand why things are the way they are in the present (Deakin University, 2021). This was conducted using primary and secondary sources from the past, studies, journal articles, and some personal accounts from the present. The primary accounts were mostly autobiographies of people from the past, sometimes written by the people themselves or dictated by others. Many of the secondhand accounts come from modern historians trying to better understand a specific point in history through the thoughts of people who lived during that time. Studies and books investigating Black mental health were used for information about modern-day African Americans and often included supplemental anecdotes of modern-day Black people. Opinion articles by Black people talking about their experiences in the modern day and other investigative news articles were also helpful.

RESULTS

The results of this historical analysis cover the history of anti-Black racism in mental health care, as well as situations and experiences that relate to specific times in U.S. history like the Middle Passage, enslavement, post-Emancipation life, and the Civil Rights movement.

The History of Anti-Black Racism in Mental Health Care

Historically, psychology has been used to enforce already set Western ideas of racial superiority, which also served as evidence for the perceived inferiority of non-White people (Guthrie, 2004). For example, many White physicians, including George Mills Beard, a prominent neurologist, believed that Black people could not develop mental illnesses because they were too “uncivilized” (Campbell, 2007). He popularized a medical condition called neurasthenia, which is poorly defined but characterized by physical and mental exhaustion due to

emotional distress (Merriam-Webster, 2022). For Beard, neurasthenia was the result of “brain work,” meaning those who were working class and performing jobs requiring physical labor could not develop it (Campbell, 2007, p.161). This idea that mental illness required “higher thought” was not a new one and had been called the “Immunity Hypothesis” since the 1600s (Adekson, 2021, p.14). He also believed that Black and Indigenous people, those considered “barbarians” and “savages,” were not capable of “brain work” and, therefore, could not develop neurasthenia (Campbell, 2007, p. 162). Also, it was thought that it would not be worth it to investigate the psychology of Black people (Guthrie, 2004). As “uncivilized people,” it was believed that they would die off as civilization progressed forward (Guthrie, 2004, p.35).

Beard also thought that whether one developed mental illness depended on, in addition to race and class, religion and gender (Campbell, 2007). He thought only White, upper-class Protestants, those with the same gender, racial, religious, and class status as him, could develop neurasthenia with entrepreneurial or intellectual jobs that he felt helped advance civilization (Campbell, 2007). The idea of advancing civilization greatly affected how mental illness was perceived in the 1800s. Receiving a diagnosis of neurasthenia was celebrated due to the exclusivity of the population of people who could be diagnosed with it (Campbell, 2007). Since these people were supposed to advance civilization through their scholarly or entrepreneurial pursuits, the illness that helped form their identity and belonged exclusively to them showed the advancement of society. Therefore, those not considered civilized could not have any mental illness.

Beard wrote many of his writings about neurasthenia in 1881, the year of the earliest recorded attempt in the United States to test the psychological capabilities of non-White people (Guthrie, 2004). C.S. Myers, an anthropologist, found that Asians had slower reaction times than

White people, thereby proving White people's "superiority"(Guthrie, 2004). Shortly after, another experimenter performed a reaction time experiment on Black and Indigenous people (Guthrie, 2004). This experiment found that White people had slower reaction time, after which the experimenter said, "the reflective man is the slower being" (Guthrie, 2004, p.47). These changes in how evidence was interpreted showed how psychology was primarily used to enforce scientists' preexisting ideas about racial hierarchy and that if evidence contradicted it, they would interpret that evidence differently.

Later, however, mental illness and African Americans would have a new relationship. Edward Jarvis, a physician, challenged the belief that Black people could not experience mental illness. He commented on the results of a census claiming that insanity was more frequent among free African Americans versus those enslaved (Guthrie, 2007). Due to not being able to reconcile Black people with mental illness, mental health professionals created differences between White and Black mental illness (Campbell, 2007). Some argued that Black insanity was "of a lower order" that made an already primitive people more "violent, profane, and vulgar" (Campbell, 2007, p.173). Jarvis had predicted that the data he collected for his commentary would be misused to argue that Black people should remain in bondage, and he was correct (Campbell, 2007). Mental health professionals at the time believed that free people had a higher rate of insanity because, without slaveholders, they were acting out violently (Campbell, 2007). This was a part of the "Exaggerated Risk Hypothesis," which said that Black people were at greater risk for mental illness (Adekson, 2021). Many supporters of slavery felt enslaved people escaped because they were treated too much like equals by their masters (Guthrie, 2004).

One of these people was a physician named Samuel Cartwright, who said enslaved people ran away due to a disorder called drapetomania, a disease that, according to him, was

common among Black people and cats (Guthrie, 2004). Drapetomania was supposedly caused by a slaveholder being too familiar with enslaved people (Perzichilli, 2020), and the cure was to whip them whenever they seemed “sulky and dissatisfied” (Guthrie, 2004, p. 116). He also thought enslaved people could catch Dyaesthesia Aethiopsis (Guthrie, 2004). Symptoms included “stupidness of mind,” destroying everything they handle, wandering at night, being sleepy during the day, and not doing work (Guthrie, 2004, p. 116). According to Cartwright, it is cured by cleaning them, rubbing them in oil, and making them do harder labor (Guthrie, 2004). Unlike White mental illness, which was thought of as the result of the burden of shouldering the noble responsibility of advancing civilization, Black mental illness was the fault of Black people’s own moral weakness (Campbell, 2007).

In addition to corporal punishment as a “cure” for Dysethesia Aethiopsis, Cartwright suggested the idea of internment work camps as a way to “help” ailing Black people (Washington, 2006). They were generally not allowed to go into asylums, so they would be put into jails instead (Washington, 2006). These are the beginnings of the associations between Black people, imprisonment, and criminality that continue into modern times. In 1984, a 66-year-old grandmother named Eleanor Bumpurs was shot and had been diagnosed as psychotic by a psychiatrist sent over by New York City after maintenance workers found cans of feces in her bathtub (Lebron, 2017). The police were sent to take her to a mental health facility, and they forced their way into her apartment to find her naked and carrying a kitchen knife (Lebron, 2017). Although there were six officers carrying guns, she, alone with her knife, was shot nine times and killed (Lebron, 2017). Instead of receiving mental health help, she received the ultimate punishment by police, thereby deeming her a threat and a criminal. Her story fits into the present-day finds that Black people with mental illnesses are more likely to be killed by law

enforcement (Adekson, 2021). Also, African Americans with psychosis-related conditions are more likely to be incarcerated without treatment, and 64 percent of incarcerated people experience mental health issues (Adekson, 2021).

Cartwright was a polygenist, believing all human races had different origins and were specifically made to be in various natural environments (Washington, 2006). For example, he thought that the tropical climate of Africa made Black people immune to malaria and yellow fever, among other diseases, and fit to work in the mosquito-infested U.S. South (Washington, 2006). This idea that Black people were inferior people with genes that allowed them to withstand conditions that White people could not was a contradiction (Washington, 2006). Fredrick Douglass pointed out that many polygenists were White enslavers who were interested in interpreting evidence according to their biases (Washington, 2006). Today, about 86 percent of psychologists are White, and research has found that there is a lot of provider bias and stereotyping in the mental health field (Perzichilli, 2020) and that biases lead to negative treatment of Black clients and mistrust on the part of the client (Adekson, 2021). This can be used to show why more people of color should be in the mental health field.

For all the claims of Black stupidity, enslavers trusted the enslaved with many tasks that they should not have been trusted with if they were as unintelligent as was said (Washington, 2006). Many enslaved people held positions as herbalists, midwives, nurses, farm equipment operators, inventors, and physicians' apprentices (Washington, 2006). In fact, many owners knew how intelligent some of the enslaved were because when trying to catch those who ran away, they would have to put an honest description to catch them (Washington, 2006). In newspapers, some runaways were described as "artful, well-spoken, crafty, and intelligent"

(Washington, 2006, p. 42). Other newspaper notices described many enslaved people who were not only literate but also polyglots (Washington, 2006).

Mental testing was done on kids as early as 1897 and grew in popularity with the belief that abilities could be inherited and biologically measured (Guthrie, 2004). In 1897, 1,000 kids, half of them Black and half of them White, were chosen for a memory experiment in which they read poetry and had to repeat everything they remembered (Guthrie, 2004). In this experiment, the Black children performed better overall; after that, memory tests were assumed to be invalid (Guthrie, 2004). In 1914, B.A. Phillips compared the test scores of about 137 white and 86 black kids (Guthrie, 2004). The results prompted him to conclude that Black people were best suited for manual labor (Guthrie, 2004). During World War I, the U.S. military conducted intelligence tests among their Black soldiers that, for the military officers, further proved the inferiority of Black people (Guthrie, 2004). Lighter-skinned soldiers tended to receive higher scores on these tests; those who conducted the tests concluded that their White ancestry made them more intelligent (Guthrie, 2004). Some craniologists, including one named Robert Bean, used skull measurements to confirm his belief that they were incapable of intelligent thought or reason (Guthrie, 2004).

Eugenicists tended to believe that inferiority created inferiority and superiority produced superiority (Guthrie, 2004). This fed the idea that those considered inferior would give birth to inferior people. By 1930, 24 states had laws that allowed the sterilization of people with “unfit traits,” people with mental illness, poor people, the “feeble-minded,” drunks, people with epilepsy, and the “criminalistic” (Guthrie, 2004, p.100). All of these descriptors are attributes that have been historically assigned to Black people. Even in the 1970s, some doctors wanted Black people with an I.Q. of under 100 to be sterilized in exchange for cash (Guthrie, 2004). In

fact, in 1973, a former President of the American Psychological Association, Henry Garrett, said that Black peoples' brains were less complex than those of White people (Guthrie, 2004).

For as long as schizophrenia has been known to be a mental illness, it had been thought of as a disease that primarily affected White middle-class women until the Civil Rights Movement (Burroughs, 2022). Much like how ideas of insanity changed after Emancipation due to Black social progress, mental health professionals began to differentiate between schizophrenia for White people and Black people (Burroughs, 2022). One 1968 article from the *Archives of General Psychiatry* described it as a "protest psychosis" brought on by listening to groups like the Black Panthers or the Nation of Islam (Perzichilli, 2020). Groups that had "delusional anti-Whiteness" and held "aggressive" feelings about the social order in the United States (Perzichilli, 2020). According to this article, Black Power Movements are what drove Black men to insanity (Burroughs, 2022, p.8), and the media used this to warn people about Black schizophrenic killers on the loose, helping to solidify the general idea of schizophrenia as a mental illness for angry Black men (Perzichilli, 2020).

The effects of these campaigns can be seen in the way rate at which Black people are diagnosed with schizophrenic and other psychotic spectrum disorders in the present day. African Americans are about four times more likely to be diagnosed with schizophrenia, which, like in the '60s, is related to the idea that Black people are overly paranoid (Adekson, 2021). Paranoia, which in some cases can be termed "healthy cultural paranoia," and can be mistaken for paranoia (Adekson, 2021, p. 51). Clinicians tend to focus more on psychotic symptoms than major depression when it comes to African Americans, which results in over-diagnoses of psychotic disorders and underdiagnoses of mood disorders (Adekson, 2021).

The Middle Passage

The Middle Passage was the 21–90 day journey that carried enslaved Africans from Africa to the Americas and the Caribbean in exchange for goods from these places (Britannica, 2022). The journey involved being shackled with other kidnapped people in tight and unsanitary quarters, disease, and death while being physically, emotionally, and psychologically tortured by the crew members (Britannica, 2022). It is also called the *Maafa*, which means tragedy or disaster in Kiswahili (Acree, 2022), and the Black African Holocaust (Walker, 2020) because of the millions of people that died during the journey (DeGruy, 2017). The trade started around 1518 (Britannica, 2022); however, the first boat of enslaved people that arrived in what is now the United States landed in the colonial settlement of Jamestown, Virginia, in 1619, which is a fairly well-known year (Hannah-Jones et al., 2021). Not as well-known is the year that the last ship of 116 enslaved people landed on United States shores, 1860 (Durkin, 2019). On this ship was a man with the birth name of Oluale Kossula and the enslavement name of Cudjo Lewis, who was kidnapped from a place that is now part of Nigeria (Hurstun, 2018).

From the time that slavery was legal in the United States into the 1930s, many former enslaved people wrote down their life story or recounted it to others; however, there are very few narratives about people's time on the Middle Passage (Durkin, 2019) and Kossula's story is one of the few. His story shows how the trauma of the Middle Passage can start long before they see any ships. Kossula, as he liked to be called by Hurstun, was kidnapped when his village was raided by warriors from the kingdom of Dahomey, including the famous Dahomey Amazons, and witnessed people being wantonly beheaded and killed (Hurstun, 2018). Zora Neale Hurstun, a literary fiction author and anthropologist, who recorded his life as dictated by him in *Barracoon: The Story of the Last "Black Cargo"*, noted that when he was talking about his

kidnapping, not only could she hear his agony and pain, but she also felt as though he was no longer mentally with her and had forgotten that she was there (Hurstun, 2018).

Another survivor of that last ship, the *Clotilda*, was a woman named Sally Smith, who also went by the supposed West African name Redoshi, although that name does not exist in West Africa (Durkin, 2019). It is unclear whether Redoshi was West African as there is also evidence that she was from West Central Africa, but she was definitely a captive on the *Clotilda*, which sailed off the coast of West Africa (Durkin, 2019). When discussing her experience on the Middle Passage, she talks about it being four months long, even though historian Sylviane Diouf calculated that it would have lasted about 45 days, which may display the depth of the psychological trauma she experienced (Durkin, 2019). She was interviewed many times by many people, including Hurstun; however, during an interview with an author and voting rights activist named Amelia Boyton Robinson, Robinson noted that Redoshi was crying while recording her story, which may have been her mentally reliving her experiences (Durkin, 2019). When his story was being recorded, Kossula was in his 80s, and while it is not clear exactly how old Redoshi was, she was elderly (Durkin, 2019). In modern times, a concern when it comes to the mental health of elderly Black people is that they may often relive or reexperience racially traumatic events from their past (Adekson, 2021), and based on the descriptions given, it seems that Kossula and Redoshi may have been reliving the experience of their kidnappings and overall suffering.

Enslavers were aware of the psychological effects of capture very early, as shown by the knowledge of a condition called “the lethargy” that captured people were known to develop if they saw their relatives killed in front of them, which might be recognized as Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (Olusoga, 2021, p.3). Symptoms included being sluggish, sleepy, and inattentive

(Mustakeem, 2016). It was known that many would not recover from this as many would like people with the “lethargick disorder” would develop a fever, high pulse, and weak breath (Mustakeem, 2016, p.111). Therefore, many ship captains made sure to factor in a captive’s mental state, one telling his crew not to bring any “lunaticks,” “idiots,” or “lethargicks” because it was assumed they would not survive the journey (Mustakeem, 2016, pp.108-109). One group of captives was described as coming onto the ships “naturally sad, sluggish, peevisish,” “natural cowards,” and overall, in emotional distress and stress (Mustakeem, 2016, pp.109-110). Today, African Americans are more likely to be victims of violent crimes, and PTSD is a common diagnosis in the aftermath of these experiences (Adekson, 2021). While the experiences of captives and African Americans in the present day may have to do with their race, PTSD is different from racial trauma. Racial trauma, which is not a clinical diagnosis, is directly related to “...the events of danger related to real or perceived experiences of racial discrimination.” (Archer, 2021, p. 94-95), while PTSD is the result of witnessing, learning about, or being exposed to any type of violence (DeGruy, 2017).

On the journey, captives were known to have emotional outbursts (Mustakeem, 2016). One surgeon, who had just bought a man, felt he should not have after the man “threw himself about in an extraordinary and shewed every sign of being mad” (Mustakeem, 2016, p. 114). Many female captives were spoken about with very gendered terms, with one ship physician saying an “ exquisite degree of insensibility was particularly pervasive among the women” and that they would break out into “violent hysteric fits” (Mustakeem, 2016, p. 118). For the sailors, the captive’s sadness often meant defiance (Mustakeem, 2016). An example is how many captives refused to eat during the journey (Mustakeem, 2016). While the sailors thought it was an attempt at suicide, the author of *Slavery at Sea: Terror, Sex, and Sickness in the Middle Passage*

posits that it may have been appetite suppression as a result of experiencing trauma (Mustakeem, 2016). Olaudah Equiano, a formerly enslaved person from the Igbo tribe in what was then the Kingdom of Benin but is now part of Nigeria, was one of the most well-known Africans of the 18th century. His slave narrative, *The Interesting Narrative of the of the Life of Olaudah Equiano*, describes how while making the land journey to a slave market, he was so sad that he did not feel like eating (Equiano and Allison, 2007), and this may have been that same phenomenon of appetite suppression.

It was thought that violence was the only way to keep the captives in line, so punishment was consistently enforced (Mustakeem, 2016). In one case, flogging was how one captive's refusal to eat was dealt with, although he ended up dying regardless (Mustakeem, 2016). If flogging failed to keep a captive in line, they were put into individual shackles (Mustakeem, 2016). Examples like this seem to be the beginning of a long thread of violent punishments being used as a mental health treatment for Black people. One very common way in which captives tried to resist or self-sabotage was through suicide by jumping overboard (Mustakeem, 2016). This may have been the most comforting form of resistance because some captives believed the ocean was a portal to a spirit world where they would be reincarnated, although, for some, it may have simply been despair (Mustakeem, 2016). Redoshi talks about feeling so sick that she wanted to die (Durkin, 2019).

Although the causes are different, Black suicide is a phenomenon that continues today. In 2007 it was the leading cause of death of Black males ages 15 to 24 (Logan et al., 2007). According to a study from 2016, as suicide among white kids was decreasing, suicide among Black kids was increasing, with the suicide rate of Black children ages five to eleven exceeding that of their white peers (Walker, 2020, pp. 2). In the Black community, suicide is thought of as a

thing that only White people do, and those who commit suicide are considered weak, possibly explaining why suicide is not addressed in Black communities (Walker, 2020, pp. 3). This is a contrast to how during the Middle Passage, it was seen by captives as a show of defiance and strength (Mustakeem, 2016).

Black children in particular are at risk if they are already struggling with their mental health, come from a lower socioeconomic background, have experienced much racism in their lives, or belong to sexual and gender minority groups (Opara et al., 2020). Depending on where they live, some children can become exposed to violence regularly, resulting in Post-Traumatic Stress or depression that they may not receive help for due to their economic situation (Opara et al., 2020). Often, racism can affect their self-worth negatively, which can lead to suicidal ideation (Opara et al., 2020). While the suicides of people on the Middle Passage may have resulted from symptoms of PTSD, the suicides of Black people now seem to be the culmination of racial trauma. Being of lower socioeconomic status, being exposed to violence, and not having access to adequate mental health care are all the result of generations of systemic racism, so any trauma stemming from that could be classified as racial trauma.

Some surgeons opted to find ways to keep the captives happy to prevent them from getting sick (Mustakeem, 2016). One way would be to give them alcohol to reduce anxiety and make them more docile, and they would let married couples and other family members stay together because it made them happy, and therefore, they would not self-sabotage (Mustakeem, 2016). Equiano, in his narrative, describes being given alcohol once he was aboard the ship and a time during the long land journey in which he was reunited with his sister he had been separated from (Equiano and Allison, 2007). When their relationship was known, it was ensured that they

were kept together (Equiano and Allison, 2007). This is an early example of the importance of community for the mental well-being of Black people in the U.S.

Other ways that sailors were told to keep up captives' spirits was by letting them play the drums and dance (Mustakeem, 2016). The captives thought of drums as tools that called the spirits (Mustakeem, 2016) and were a way to pray for assistance (Mustakeem, 2016). That was expressed by singing "melancholy songs," as some sailors reported (Mustakeem, 2016, p. 120). While this would have provided comfort, in some cases, captives were made to sing and dance by the sailors under the threat of physical abuse (Mustakeem, 2016). Music and other forms of art have provided comfort during hard times, and while this tradition goes back to pre-colonial Africa, this seems to be the beginning of this phenomenon for African Americans (Philipp, 2017).

Enslavement

Slave narratives provide a glimpse into how nightmarish enslavement could be. Frederick Douglass described witnessing his loved ones being physically assaulted, being whipped and beaten himself, and being made to work in harsh weather conditions (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). Sojourner Truth, in her narrative, recounted her poor living conditions, having family members sold away from her, being beaten and lied to by her enslavers, and historians think that sexual assault is also implied in the text (Truth and Perry, 2005). Harriet Jacobs revealed witnessing her enslavers verbally abusing the people they enslaved, physically abusing them including shoving food down their throats, escaping and having to leave her children, and implied that she was sexually abused (Jacobs, 1861).

What is unique about female slave narratives are the descriptions of the trials being a mother and being sexual assaulted. Truth could not read or write and so she had her narrative written down by Olive Gilbert. When alluding to Truth's assault, Gilbert noted that there are some things that could be not talked about because of "delicacy" or inflicting "undeserved pain on some now living" (Truth and Perry, 2005, p. 21), so we cannot know its effect on her although this would imply that she talked to at least one person about it. While both Truth and Gilbert may have meant well by excluding what happened to her, this showcased the culture of silence in the Black community about sexual assault that continues to this day (Broussard, 2013). Jacobs' narrative was a standout at the time of its publishing because while she never directly talks about her sexual abuse, it is made clear to the audience what she is talking about. She described her enslaver as someone who "peopled my young mind with unclean images" (Jacobs, 1861, p.44), calls him a "vile monster" (Jacobs, 1861, p.44), a "shadow" that "dogged" her (Jacobs, 1861, p.46), states that he caused her "fear and sorrows" (Jacobs, 1861, p.47), and talks about enslaved women having to evade the wrath of his wife (Jacobs, 1861). Jacobs' experience would make her one of the 58 percent of enslaved women aged 15-30 who were assaulted by White men and unfortunately, that legacy persists today (West and Johnson, 2013).

Today, around one in four Black women will be sexually abused before the age of 18 and one in five report that they have been raped (APA, 2020). Forty to sixty percent reported having coercive sexual contact by age 18 (APA, 2020) and risk of sexual assault is higher for Black women who are low-income, incarcerated, or from a sexual minority (West and Johnson, 2013). It is hard to discern how sexual violence may have affected enslaved women psychologically due to the code of silence around discussing it, however, that silence is slowly breaking, and we can see based on surveys, the mental health repercussions Black women who have been raped in the

modern-day face. In a survey of Black college women, about 75 percent of the participants had symptoms of PTSD and those who have experienced multiple forms of sexual violence were more prone to PTSD, depression, and suicidal ideation (West and Johnson, 2013). Among this population those who held beliefs that women are sexual objects and believed that Black women are promiscuous held lower self-esteem (West and Johnson, 2013). It is unclear whether Harriet Jacobs held these views; although these stereotypes were pervasive during her time, she talks about feelings shame in talking about it to other women in her life (Jacobs, 1861).

While the harm inflicted on enslaved people was often physically violent, sometimes there was heavy psychological manipulation. In their narratives, both Sojourner Truth and Frederick Douglass conveyed how celebrations were used to keep them servile. Truth recounts a time when she had successfully gotten away from her enslaver but had gone back in order to celebrate Pinkster. This was a holiday celebrated seven days after Easter where Black New Yorkers mock the European upper class and are allowed to let go of their inhibitions (Truth and Perry, 2005). As she was about to go back to her enslaver, according to her, she received a vision from God that compelled her to go run back to freedom (Truth and Perry, 2005). This can be read as her realizing that Pinkster was a tool to keep her enslaved and to keep her from running back to freedom (Truth and Perry, 2005). According to Douglass, between Christmas and New Year's Eve, they did not have to work and played games, danced, and got drunk (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). If they did not participate, they were considered ungrateful, and the enslavers even played gambling games that required some of the enslaved to get as drunk as possible (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). He believes that this was a tactic to take their minds off the possibility of revolting and to give them a taste of freedom so overwhelming that they would not want it (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003).

While describing his time before emancipation, Kossula said that other enslaved people (American colored folks as he called them) made fun of the way that he and other African-born enslaved people spoke (Hurston, 2018). He also described the American-born enslaved laughing and calling the African-born savages when they celebrated the news of their emancipation by dancing in an African style (Hurston, 2018). The way Kossula was treated by other Black people may be an example of internalized racism within the American-born enslaved. Internalized racism can refer to the extent to which one adopts and accepts negative messages and belief about one's racial group (Banks and Stephens, 2018). While the ridicule would have severe consequences for his family in their post-Emancipation life, this mockery was most likely a defense mechanism for the American-born enslaved.

The destruction of security, physically and psychologically, could have led to an enslaved person identifying with their enslaver, escaping, or attacking them (Guthrie, 2004). By identifying with their enslaver, an enslaved person could avoid their own feelings of the helplessness of their situation (Guthrie, 2004). Internalized racism in the modern day can also be a form of protection called appropriated oppression, in which members of oppressed groups learn how to use the tactics of oppressors to gain some perceived advantage over oppression (Banks & Stephens, 2018). Examples could include a Black person who believes that Black people are lazy and works extremely hard to prove that they are not one of those Black people or a Black person who is good at basketball and works hard to excel in it due to this belief (Banks & Stephens, 2018). Hard work and achievement are often ways of counteracting racial oppression, and this is what these people would be doing, even though their achievements are based on racist ideas (Banks & Stephens, 2018).

Going back to Harriet Jacobs 'story, while her story highlights the double bind of being a Black female enslaved person, it also displays the power of community. Jacobs describes her childhood as a happy time where she did not even realize she was enslaved until she was 6 years old (Jacobs, 1861). Part of this may have been because her family members practiced trades that allowed them to earn money, so long as some of it was given to their enslaver (Jacobs, 1861). This allowed Jacobs and her brother "many comforts" as she put it (Jacobs, 1861, p.2). She also had her father, mother, and grandmother together and their enslaver favored her mother allowing Jacobs the privilege of not performing any strenuous tasks (Jacobs, 1861). When she escaped in adulthood, her family members protected her even at the threat of imprisonment in addition to her grandmother and her grandmother's friend sheltering her (Jacobs, 1861). Not only did her community protect her from feeling the worst emotional effects of slavery for the first part of her life, they also physically protected her from being recaptured.

Even today, community, which can include kinship care, religious community, or racial socialization, can be an important part of healing and mitigating the effects of racism for African Americans (Adekson, 2021). It is proven that kinship care, a system in which people outside the nuclear family help raise a child, can reduce stress and promote stability, especially if a child's parents are not around (Austin, 2020). This is what Harriet Jacobs experienced being raised in part by her grandparents, aunts, and uncles (Jacobs, 1861), which would have been necessary during enslavement as nuclear families were often sold away from each other. Around 25 percent of kids in foster care are Black despite Black kids being about 14 percent of the U.S. population, so the legacy of Black families not being together continues (Austin, 2020). Sojourner Truth found community in religious services, through which she seemed to find freedom, status as a preacher, and reunited her with various family members (Truth and Perry, 2003). Today, Black

churches are places that can facilitate emotional closeness, where people can find leadership positions, and involvement in it can be associated with lower rates of depression and suicide (Belgrave and Allison, 2018).

After his escape, Fredrick Douglass describes feeling as though he saw every White person as an enemy and could not even trust other Black people (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). He later talks about how receiving help from a free African American and going to abolitionist meetings helped him work through these feelings. Racial socialization is how one comes to understand their racial group and their position in the world (DeGruy, 2017) and positive racial socialization is a way of facilitating a positive image of one's racial group, which can come from interacting with other Black people (Stokes et al., 2020). In the modern day, this has been shown to mitigate the internalization of negative messages about Black people (DeGruy, 2017).

Storytelling and music are ways that Black people in the past and present have been able to cope with subjugation. Storytelling is a way of educating and racial socialization that can help build resilience (DeGruy, 2017). It has been proven that kids who know their history have higher self-esteem, felt more secure, and were better at facing challenges (DeGruy, 2017). Slave narratives were a way of doing this since they discuss important African American history and provide education on life as an enslaved person. In addition to families telling stories about their ancestors to each other, in the modern day, authors like Isabel Wilkerson try to tell untold stories about significant times in Black history, such as the Great Migration. Fredrick Douglass recounted listening to other enslaved people sing as they had to go work in their enslaver's plantation house with, in his words "at once the highest joy and the deepest sadness"(Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). When he eventually got to the North, he found that some northerners thought that the enslaved expressed pleasure at their conditions through singing (Douglass and

O'Meally, 2003). He said that that was not the case; enslaved people, himself included, would sing to express their sadness (Douglass and O'Meally, 2003). Today, popular music, especially rap is used to express frustration, anger, and passion. This is something that becomes particularly relevant during the Harlem Renaissance in the 1920s.

Reconstruction and the Black Codes

The Emancipation Proclamation was issued in 1863 however, the Civil War did not end until 1865 so Reconstruction, a period of around 12 years in which Black Americans started to recover from slavery, did not start until then (Hannah-Jones et al., 2021). During this period, Black Americans gained citizenship, the Civil Rights Act of 1875, and access to higher education and leading to more economic freedom (Hannah-Jones et al., al, 2021). These advancements gave Black people the prospect of something that had largely been denied to them: respect. At least, this was the goal of all the reforms of Reconstruction; however, the Black codes, a set of laws made to control the movements of newly freed people were put in place the same year that the war ended (DeGruy, 2017). Black kids in the South learned at an early age that they had to pay deference to White people even while being disrespected themselves (Litwack, 1998). These contradictions included anything from having to remove one's hat when talking to a White person but a White person not having to remove their hat when talking to a Black person, to a White people being allowed to address Black people as the n-word, but a Black person not being able to look a White person in the eye (Litwack, 1998). Parents taught their kids to contain their rage and act with restraint when confronted with these situations (Litwack, 1998).

Respect is something that African Americans were denied while enslaved and that continued after emancipation. In the modern day, Black people continue to face disrespect through the perpetual denial of civil rights and many African Americans have a specific

sensitivity to being disrespected especially from other Black people, according to DeGruy (2017). In *Post Traumatic Slave Syndrome*, she recounts the story of a Black client of her social worker daughter who killed a drug dealer he owed money to after he called him a “bitch” in front of his partner and child (DeGruy, 2017, p.147). DeGruy’s daughter was baffled as to why a 17-year-old who was just released from prison got so angry that he beat someone to death, but DeGruy believes that his fragile sense of and manhood could not stand humiliation and disrespect (DeGruy, 2017). This story is similar to the story of Oluale Kossula’s son, Cudjo Lewis Jr.

Post Emancipation, Kossula, his wife, and other former enslaved people started a community called Africa Town, where they raised their family (Hurstun, 2018). He says that the discrimination he and other African-born Black people faced from American-born Black people continued towards his kids (Hurstun, 2018). Growing up they were called savages, monkeys, and cannibals (Hurstun, 2018), and this displays one of the two levels of shame that is associated with internalized racism, the shame associated with African-ness (Watts- Jones, 2002). Kossula believes that this caused them to lash out at other kids causing others in the community to be wary of them (Hurstun, 2018). His son, Cudjo Jr, was later sentenced to five years in prison for manslaughter and went through the convict leasing system before being pardoned (Hurstun, 2018) and eventually killed by Africa Town’s sheriff in 1902 but it was not clear why there was not an attempted arrest before his murder (Hurstun, 2018).

The convict lease system was a system in which prisoners were leased out to businesses, including plantations for, their labor (DeGruy, 2017). It is estimated a quarter of Black leased convicts died under lease (DeGruy, 2017). This may have been because the demanding pace of the work that would have resulted in beatings and working conditions that resulted in diseases

like malaria and dysentery (Litwack, 1998). The convict lease system used a loophole in the 13th amendment that abolished slavery except as a punishment for slavery, so they used this to unofficially reinstate slavery by arresting more Black people (DeGruy, 2017). Not only was this done through overly rigid Black code laws that outlawed unemployment for Black people, but also falsifying charges (DeGruy, 2017). Sexual assault could be looking at a White woman, and disturbing the peace could mean walking on the wrong side of the street (DeGruy, 2017). Many Black people's fear of imprisonment and despair at the injustice of the legal system was expressed in Blues music, which was becoming a popular form of music into the 20th century (Litwack, 1998). If convicts got out, they returned with "battered bodies and minds and vivid memories" (Litwack, 1998, p.276).

The legacy of the convict leasing system continues into the modern day as the United States has the highest incarceration rate in the world with about 750 of every 100,000 people being in jail or prison (Alexander, 2020). African Americans make up 35 percent of the incarcerated population despite being 13 percent of the general population (Mahaffey et al., 2018). White people are more likely to engage in drug crime, while Black people are more likely to be sent to prison for it (Alexander, 2020) and they also tend to serve longer sentences of similar crimes (Mahaffrey et al.,2018). According to a study of 250 African American male ex-prisoners in Kentucky, 29 percent of them reported psychological problems, 20 percent had mental breakdowns in the year before going to prison, and 72 percent reported using alcohol after their release (Mahaffrey et al., 2018). Those that use alcohol every day after their release are 4.63 times more likely to reported psychological problems (Mahaffrey et al., 2018).

Due, in part, to the convict lease system, Black southerners came to view law enforcement with as an "alien force" and "repressive", with one Black newspaper editor

proclaiming in a speech “WE HAVE NO CONFIDENCE IN WHITE POLICEMEN” (Litwack, 1998, p. 277). The excessive force that police used, often using any reason to take the opportunity to beat Black kids, made them feel vulnerable (Litwack, 1998). Much of the White population also took it upon themselves to police Black people using the idea of punishing Black criminals to start riots that destroyed Black property and killed people (Litwack, 1998). In the aftermath of one 1906 Atlanta riot, some felt fearful and deeply disillusioned, as though they did not have a home (Litwack, 1998). Aggressive policing is something that continues today and has negative mental health effects on people today especially young men of color in urban cities. A 2013 study of 1261 young men in New York found that those who have had had more police contact have higher anxiety scores and more trauma symptoms (Geller et al., 2014).

In the wake of Reconstruction, Black people who tried to do things that have historically been reserved for white people, like receive higher education, were shut out of the economic opportunities available for White people, as was the case for a man named Willie Holcombe (Litwack, 1998). In his case, after he failed to find opportunities, he turned to alcohol and started “gittin’ mean” according to his father until he died when he was seemingly attacked by a group of White men (Litwack, 1998, p. 5). In the modern day, Black people can be shut out of institutions and beaten the way Willie Holcombe was, but more often experience microaggressions, which are comments that, intentionally or not, disparage someone based on characteristic associated with their group (Winters, 2020). Navigating a mostly White power structure can lead to stress since microaggressions and often being the only Black person in the room can remind someone that they do not belong (Winters, 2020). It is also documented that Black health outcomes get worse as socioeconomic status rises and this can be attributed to the stress of having to navigate majority White spaces (Winters, 2020).

It is clear that Willie Holcombe's mental health declined after his experiences in an environment originally built for White people since he started to drink more, and a similar phenomenon can happen to Black people now. In 1903, a former governor of North Carolina said that "The truth is the negro is going to fare best and be happiest when his position is most subordinate" (Litwack, 1998, p. 149). He further noted that Black people who are prosperous deserve pity for all the danger they are in (Litwack, 1998). Even through this fervent racism, he makes a strong point about how deadly violence was often aimed at more successful Black people. This shows another example of the danger in seeking any non-subservient position in a White power structure (Litwack, 1998).

For Black children, with the newfound freedom to attend school came exposure to "the superiority of Anglo-Saxon institutions" (Litwack, 1998, p.71). They were taught uncritical histories of the Pilgrims and the Founding Fathers and when they were taught about their own histories, it was of a lowly, idiotic people who were happily taken from uncivilized Africa and brought to the New World (Litwack, 1998). One observer recounted hearing a group of Black school children sing songs glorifying the Confederacy (Litwack, 1998). At home, many students were taught about Black leaders and Black people as far back as the Revolution (Litwack, 1998). This caused indifference or even hostility towards what they were learning in school (Litwack, 1998).

We see a lack of education about Black history in the modern day. In talking about his experience in school, one Black teacher talks about how he received an education that is not very different to the one Black kids received a century or two prior (Edelin, 2022). He noticed that this type of education produces shame, lower sense of self, and lower sense of pride in their racial group (Edelin, 2022). In fact, kids could develop "cultural amnesia", when lack of

knowledge about one's culture can lead to an adoption of a foreign identity, culture, and history (Edelin, 2022).

These scenarios of Black people within White power structures and how Black children experience education in the United States are examples of double consciousness. This was a term coined by W.E.B. Du Bois, in his 1903 essay collection, *The Souls of Black Folks*. Double consciousness described the idea that Black people are constantly trying to reconcile two conflicting identities, being Black and being American. DuBois also believed this meant that Black people were seeing themselves through the eyes of White people (Du Bois, 2012). Ultimately, it creates internal conflict that the “dogged strength alone” of the body keeps it from “being torn asunder” (Du Bois, 2012, p.9). In the examples of Black people in White power structures, people are striving for things that are considered to be for White people such as a top position in a company or an education. In the case of some modern-day Black people in the workplace, this dual-identity conflict has a negative effect on their body as well as their mind.

The Rise of the “New Negro”

The Harlem Renaissance or, the New Negro movement as it was called in its day, was a time in the 1920s in which what it meant to be an African American was changing (Lebron, 2017). For Black people, the “New Negro” was someone who was well educated and determined to break out of a degrading dependence on White people (Litwack, 1998). The man who coined the term, Alain Locke, meant for the “New Negro” to be someone who viewed their Blackness positively and viewed art as an important vehicle to racial uplift (Lebron, 2017). W.E.B Dubois thought that African Americans viewed the world through both a Black and White lens, and Locke thought that Black people should work on viewing the world solely through their own eyes (Lebron, 2017). The way for this was paved by the Great Migration during the 1910s and

1920s where millions of African Americans moved from the South to the North to attempt to get away from violence, voter suppression, and to take advantage of the jobs that were newly available in the wake of World War I (Lebron, 2017). The ideas of the “New Negro” were also influential going into how many young African Americans behaved during the eventual second World War.

The Warmth of Other Suns provides an account of the lives and journeys of three Southerners who migrated North and West between around 1915-1970, including Ida Mae Gladney who migrated during the Great Depression, George Starling who migrated after World War II, and Robert Pershing Foster who migrated during the 1950s (Wilkerson, 2011). They migrated for better employment opportunities, for their dignity, and to escape lynching (Wilkerson, 2011). Ida Mae Gladney grew up in a Mississippi where violence against Black people was the norm in the form of beatings, lynchings, and directly personal violence Ida herself experienced when two White men almost threw her down a well (Wilkerson, 2011). It makes sense then that when a planter who was looking for her husband’s cousin threatened to hit her, that she said to his companion, “That’s alright. Let ‘em hit me” (Wilkerson, 2011, p. 126). That numbness is a symptom of segregation stress syndrome, which are a collection of intergenerational symptoms similar to PTSD symptoms that result from trying to survive Jim Crow (Thompson-Miller, 2011).

George Starling from Florida was constantly aware of the possibility of being lynched, but he tried to live his life with his head held up high, which was dangerous for a Black man in the South (Wilkerson, 2011). In fact, other Black people, including his wife, wondered why he could not just accept his place (Wilkerson, 2011). As a fruit picker, he tried to rally his fellow workers to protest for appropriate pay, but they told their employer, who had the intention of

lynching George (Wilkerson, 2011). George escaped to Harlem angry at the South, an anger that the author of *The Warmth of Other Suns* said she could feel as he was recounting it decades later (Wilkerson, 2011).

Robert Pershing Foster had a more privileged upbringing as the son of college educated Black parents, one of the few in his Louisiana town (Wilkerson, 2011). This put him in a social standing high enough to know the dignity he and his family were being denied by the dominant society, through Jim Crow. He went to a historically Black college, Morehouse College, in Atlanta, where he saw successful Black people living life in a way that Jim Crow did not allow for most people, and this was something that brought him peace (Wilkerson, 2011). This is another example of how racial pride and seeing other Black people succeed can help one's own mental health. After he had graduated and finished medical school, he found that Jim Crow stifled his job opportunities and felt that his prospects would be better if he moved to California (Wilkerson, 2011).

Using a two-year study from 2001 of 3,004 African American adults, it was found that migrants and northern stayers, those whose mothers were also born and raised in the North, had higher odds of lifetime mental health disorders, mood, anxiety, and substance use disorder than those raised in the South (Vu, 2022). Although the data does not include the children of migrants, it should be noted that George Starling's son struggled with addiction for a large part of his life. Migrants also had higher rates of self-reported racial discrimination (Vu, 2022), all of which correlates with the lower physical outcomes among this group as well. The three individuals at the center of *The Warmth of Other Suns* all faced new challenges. Among the racial violence that came with the influx of Black migrants, White residents leaving areas in Chicago, where Ida Mae was, and New York where Black migrants went, caused de facto segregation (Wilkerson,

2011). Ida Mae and her husband's jobs were not much better than sharecropping; George had a job that still took him to the South, so he experienced Jim Crow, and upon going to California, Robert learned that being in the West did not mean segregation was gone (Wilkerson, 2011). Many migrants who did not find that "Promised Land" in the North did not express their disappointment to their family or go back to the South (Wilkerson, 2011), and this may have contributed to negative mental health outcomes.

Harlem became the center for the burgeoning cultural movement in part because 175,000 people had moved into the neighborhood by the end of the first Great Migration, turning into the largest concentration of Black people in the world (CrashCourse, 2021). Many different artists subscribed to Locke's idea that Black people should take inspiration from Africa including Richmond Barthe, Aaron Douglas, and Meta Vaux Warrick, who all used African themes in their art (CrashCourse, 2021). Barthe, in particular, was a sculptor who wanted to portray the Black body positively. Langston Hughes was a writer who not only wrote poems that harkened back to Africa but, also wrote about Black life in America, for all its joys and misfortunes, which drew criticism from some Black Americans who wanted to portray Black people in the best possible light (CrashCourse, 2021). This attitude towards portraying Black life was echoed by his friend and fellow Harlem Renaissance writer, Zora Neale Hurston (CrashCourse, 2021). Her raw portrayal of Black life in her fiction, emphasized by her writing dialogue in the Southern African American dialect she grew up with drew criticism from the Black intelligentsia who felt that her writing portrayed Black people as dumb in the eyes of White people (Heather Strain, 2023), a clear example of double consciousness, with what White people might think influencing how Black art was viewed. Both she and Hughes kept to the "New Negro" idea of not letting what White people thought determine how they lives their lives and expressed themselves

(CrashCourse, 2021). Her attitude is exemplified by this quote, “Sometime, I feel discriminated against, but it does not make me angry. It merely astonishes me. How can any deny themselves the pleasure of my company! It’s beyond me” (Lebron, 2017).

In the modern day, art therapy has principles that are similar to that of the Harlem Renaissance, especially as it relates to potential Black clients. Art has been shown to uplift and provide a sense of power and agency (Harris and Marcelo, 2021), something that was the cornerstone of the Harlem Renaissance, and which can be important for healing. Studies show racial pride and cultural affiliation, both of which were considered key traits of the “New Negro”, lead to higher self-esteem, better coping, decreased depressive symptoms, and less aggressive behaviors (Harris and Marcelo, 2021). In the study conducted by Jadea Harris and Ana Marcelo of ten college aged Black individuals, most said that expressive arts, such as dance, painting, theatre, and writing, were a way for them to express emotions they have trouble expressing, to regulate them, channel them, and have a respite from real life (2021). Some of the participants also discussed feeling a sense of racial pride, ethnic self-esteem, and comfort when they as artists felt they were supporting their community (Harris and Marcelo, 2021).

During World War II, Black soldiers struggled during training camps due to segregation and discrimination, which caused many to experience higher levels of stress and low levels of morale (Dwyer, 2006) and while there is not a lot of data from Black soldiers during World War I, the circumstances that they were under were not very different from that of World War II soldiers. They were often kept out of battles so most Black soldiers did not exhibit the same symptoms of PTSD that White soldiers did, but the tasks they were made to do like moving supplies, washing dishes, and on one notable occasion, picking cotton, contributed to the high stress and low morale (Dwyer, 2006). In letters home, many African American soldiers shared

their bitterness about the discrimination they were experiencing and on occasion, that bitterness turned into something stronger (Dwyer, 2006). One soldier, who was viewed as a troublemaker despite nothing in his background suggesting that was the case, was constantly threatened with court martial (Dwyer, 2006). He managed to get through his service; however, his experience in the military coupled with the discrimination that he witnessed and experienced back home put him in a psychiatric hospital (Dwyer, 2006). Another soldier had a breakdown while experiencing the Army's segregationist policies and had to be sent home (Dwyer, 2006).

Since then, The U.S. military has become integrated and with that, more Black soldiers have seen combat. There have been conflicting studies about whether Black service members from the Vietnam war to the Iraq war experience similar levels of PTSD or higher rates (Coleman, 2016). A study performed on veterans found that Black veterans with PTSD had higher rates of hypervigilance than White veterans with PTSD (Coleman, 2016). Although they did not have the same language for this in the 1940s, it is clear that in the example of the two soldiers and their constant awareness of the hostile environment around them led to their mental deteriorations, whether or not they actually experienced combat.

The Civil Rights Era

After World War II, African Americans became galvanized in fighting for liberty, just as they had in Europe (Hannah-Jones et al., 2021). Although most place the beginning of the Civil Rights movement after the Brown versus Board of Education decision and the Montgomery bus boycott in 1954, people like Harry T. Moore, the chief organizer for the NAACP, were registering people to vote, investigating lynchings all throughout the 1930s and 40s (Wilkerson, 2010). Over the course of the movement, millions of people protested and boycotted, enduring injury and facing death (Hannah-Jones et al., 2021). Ultimately, their efforts bore fruit through a

Voting Rights act, a second Civil Rights act, and de-segregation acts (Hannah-Jones et al., 2021). Unfortunately, the Civil Rights Movement ended with the deaths of leaders like Martin Luther King Jr. and Malcolm X.

In 1963, George Starling was on the subway when he opened his newspaper to see images of protests where Black people were being beaten by cops, pushed to the grounds, and attacked by dogs (Wilkerson, 2010). Thinking about how hard his own life was, he got so angry that he contemplated hurting a White man sitting across from him, although he was able to keep his anger in check (Wilkerson, 2010). Starling learned to channel his anger into more productive activities, including fundraising for Black churches destroyed by violence (Wilkerson, 2010). However, when Martin Luther King Jr. was assassinated, he felt numb to it (Wilkerson, 2010), again displaying how the violence he grew up with contributed to segregation stress syndrome. While it is a positive thing that Starling did not attack this random man simply for being the closest White person to him, his ability to regulate his behavior so well that the White man did not register his anger displays his lifetime of practice regulating his behavior for the appeasement of White people.

Emotional regulation, the “set of automatic and controlled processes involved in the initiation, maintenance of the occurrence, intensity, and duration of feeling states,” is something that most people do every day (Liebow & Glazer, 2019, p.128). It is often necessary when one is upset or stressed, to find a way to calm down so as not to make others uncomfortable; however, studies show that this is something that Black people find themselves doing more than White people, even in the modern day (Liebow & Glazer, 2019). Often, the purpose is to not play into stereotypes such as the “angry Black man,” even in the face of racism (Liebow & Glazer, 2019), similar to how millions of Black people like George during the Jim Crow era had to do this often

for the sake of their lives (Wilkerson, 2010). This can be contrasted with what White people can get away with, as shown in a focus group of Black professionals conducted by Adia Harvey Wingfield (2010). In talking about their workplace experiences, a few people mentioned that some of their White colleagues had had emotional outbursts with little consequence (Wingfield, 2010). At the same time, they feel they cannot even speak freely about their emotions even when experiencing microaggressions (Wingfield, 2010). One woman even got fired for speaking up about her discontent with the lack of racial diversity in her workspace (Wingfield, 2010).

Robert Pershing Foster felt that the protests were the wrong way to gain civil rights. For him, Black people needed to be better than everyone else at things (Wilkerson, 2011), which could be taken to be another example of internalized racism, but also aligns with descriptions of appropriated racial oppression, a more modern understanding of internalized racism. One aspect of appropriated racial oppression is maintaining “respectability” in the eyes of the dominant culture, which can often include trying to distance oneself from the stereotypes of Black people, like laziness or violence (Versey et al., 2019). Distancing oneself can involve achieving success in majority White spaces while criticizing the behavior of Black people, which often reaps individual success (Versey et al., 2019). Foster spent his whole life striving towards gaining the respect he felt he deserved through higher education and the medical field and is highly critical of how he saw other Black people try to gain civil rights through protests (Wilkerson, 2011). The respectability he eventually gained led to him becoming such a prominent figure in Black Los Angeles that an extravagant party he threw was reported on in the newspaper (Wilkerson, 2011). The downfall of the constant effort to maintain respectability is increased depressive symptoms, poorer sleep, and risk of chronic disease (Versey et al., 2019), but in the case of Robert Foster,

while he did develop some chronic diseases towards the end, it is hard to know if his constant vigilance about being respected is what caused it (Versey et al., 2019).

The act of protesting took an emotional toll. One respondent, who was around seven or eight years old at the time of the Montgomery bus boycott between 1954 to 1955, described her parents as being “scared” (Thompson-Miller, 2011, p.148). They had not initially wanted to boycott to avoid getting on White people’s “nerves” but started to feel bad that they did not (Thompson-Miller, 2011, p.148). In the modern day, there is a deeper understanding of how protesting affects one’s mental health. Protesting can cause high blood pressure, breathing issues, difficulty sleeping, and a collection of exhaustion, depression, and anxious feelings that could be classified under racial battle fatigue (Theis, 2020). This can also put protestors at a higher risk of PTSD (Theis, 2020).

The Civil Right Era was a time when many Black Americans sought healing from the violence they were seeing and experiencing, and for some, that meant getting in touch with their lost African heritage. For some, going to protests was healing (Thompson-Miller, 2011), but art groups like OBAC (Organization of Black American Culture) and AFRICOBRA (African Commune of Bad Relevant Artists) created art that connected members of the African diaspora with their heritage and instilled racial pride (Jarrell, 2020). Many African Americans, like Malcolm X and Muhammed Ali, had just visited, but Maya Angelou, in 1962, was one of about 200 African Americans who moved to Ghana, calling themselves the “Revolutionary Returnees” (Angelou, 1991). Moving to Ghana made sense in an era when Black Americans sought a renewed sense of racial pride, connected with their roots, and aligned themselves with decolonization movements worldwide, especially to a country with a leading Pan-Africanist, Kwame Nkrumah, as president. In Africa, for the first time, Black Americans’ skin color was

“accepted as correct and normal”, according to Maya Angelou in her autobiography, *All God's Children Need Traveling Shoes* (1991, p.3). Though she had initially moved to Ghana for her son's university education, she had “hungered for security” in Africa and, at some point, felt like she was a child who had found her way home (Angelou, 1991, p. 8).

In the modern day, research supports the assertion that Black people who are better connected with their heritage have better mental health outcomes (Walker, 2020). For many, like an American expatriate to Ghana named Lakeisha Ford, moving to Ghana included that and the benefit of not having to constantly think about being Black and all the stressors that come with it (Hjelmgaard, 2020). Many people like Sonjiah Davis, a therapist from Washington D.C., visited Ghana during the “Year of Return” in 2019, marking 400 years since enslaved people first arrived on American shores (CBS Mornings, 2021). After George Floyd's death, she felt she was on the verge of a nervous breakdown and that leaving the United States for Ghana would be the only way to help (CBS Mornings, 2021). Living in Ghana, she described herself as feeling “loved, supported, regarded, like I matter” and “liberated” (CBS Mornings, 2021).

One particularly profound story from Angelou's time in Ghana shows the healing power of getting in touch with one's ancestry. Toward the end of her time in Ghana, she went to a Ghanaian village where she met an older adult who bore a stark resemblance to her grandmother (Angelou, 1991). Upon looking at Angelou, this older woman had thought she was from the village and assumed that she was a daughter of a friend, but when it was clear that she was not even from the village, she started crying (Angelou, 1991). Angelou was then told a story about how the village had never recovered from losing its captured people during the slave trade and how the orphaned kids that were left behind, grew and told their children, who told generations after about those who were taken (Angelou, 1991). The elderly woman recognized her as a

descendant of their lost people, and Angelou started crying with her, in mourning for all the people lost, but also in celebration for having “dared to continue to love” (Angelou, 1991, p. 207).

This resembles Joy DeGruy’s experience in southern Africa in 1994 (DeGruy, 2017). She and eight other African American women were touring southern Africa to build positive relationships with African women when they stopped in Lesotho for a dinner in their honor (DeGruy, 2017). When DeGruy introduced them all, the translator went on longer than she had anticipated, but she thought nothing of it (DeGruy, 2017). When the other women started introducing themselves, the Mosotho women would clap and chant after each time (DeGruy, 2017). When DeGruy asked the translator what they were doing, he explained that most of them were from isolated villages and did not realize there were non-White Americans (DeGruy, 2017). The translator had explained to the Mosotho women that these were the descendants of those who were taken, and they were chanting a song welcoming them home (DeGruy, 2017). This led DeGruy to start sobbing, and like Maya Angelou, she was doing so out of grief for her ancestor’s pain but also in celebration that they managed to get through it (DeGruy, 2017).

One of the most high-profile Black Americans to live abroad was James Baldwin, who lived in France in the 1950s. Moving to Europe, on its face, makes less sense than moving to Africa since the objective seems to be gaining racial pride, but Baldwin and many like him simply wanted to get out of the United States and did not care too much about where they went (Baldwin, 1983). It is not as though Black Americans would not confront prejudice for the color of their skin. In *Notes of a Native Son*, we see Baldwin face prejudice in Europe, but he also posits that African Americans do not want to be confronted with their identity from reminders of American society (Baldwin, 1983). In an interview, Eddie Glaude Jr., professor of African

American Studies at Princeton who wrote a book on Baldwin, recalled his own experience visiting Germany where he witnessed an instance of police brutality against a Black man but felt liberated from having to take on the emotions related to it as he was not “their negro”, “their Black problem” (The Daily Show, 2020). This is something that other modern-day Black Americans who have moved abroad in the modern day can attest to. Those who have left for Europe often speak of finding freedom, feeling as though they are no longer just defined by race, and even though there may be institutional racism in those countries, it is not a history they are connected to and therefore feel free from (Hjelmgaard, 2020).

REFLECTION

This experience was an emotional one for me. I chose this topic not only to learn about the state of Black mental health throughout United States history but also to understand my own mental health. Throughout my four years in university, I have found taking African American Studies classes affirming and healing, so I wanted to continue that on my own. At times, I was overcome with sadness when reading the stories of people who had gone through the Middle Passage, for example, and it slowed my progress. Other times, I found it fun to read about the positive emotional effects of art movements, such as the Harlem Renaissance, my favorite time period in history, on Black Americans. Even through all the difficulty, I ultimately found it rewarding. I want to continue to build on what I have done in this project, possibly by enhancing it with interviews from modern African Americans about their lives and how they feel it relates to the past. In addition, there are some areas that I thought I could not talk about due to time constraints, one of these being the feelings and attitudes of Northern Black people during the Antebellum period, which I think can be overlooked, and I was forced to do so again here. I would explore how similar events have affected the mental health of other groups in the African

diaspora, specifically West Africans, who are from a part of the world that was heavily influenced by the slave trade.

I think my knowledge and the way I approach history were expanded. While I knew of most of the events I talked about here, thinking about them from a mental health perspective made the events more personal, especially since I connected them to events I am living through now. One surprising thing I learned was that Black people are diagnosed with schizophrenia at a higher rate than White people. The reason was not unexpected but no less interesting. It goes back to the psychological community during the Civil Rights movements tying schizophrenia to the “paranoia” of Civil Rights leaders talking about racism being at every level of American society.

This project was reading and writing, so I do not think I struggled with these aspects. While I found this rewarding, I wish I had more time to complete it. Timeliness was a struggle for me, and figuring out what to research and leave aside. If I had another year to complete this, there are many other things I would try to analyze. While I struggled with my timeliness, one of my strengths was finding historical patterns.

IMPLICATIONS

The results of this analysis show that many of the adverse events that happened in the past have echoed through to the present. They also display the ways in which African Americans have coped and shown resiliency through community, music, art, and spirituality. In many ways, there has been very little change between the past and present. Often an explanation as to why the U.S.’s history with racism no longer matters is because it was so long ago that no one can remember and that there has been too much change for it to still be relevant to modern Black

lives. Understanding history is essential, especially now, when book bans across the country are taking away the opportunity for kids to learn it. Not only can this diminish their knowledge, but for Black kids, it can cause a diminished sense of self (Edelin, 2022). In addition to displaying the connections between then and now, this project can provide mental health clinicians working with Black clients with the context to understand why Black clients might feel wary about mental health care and how the mental health care system has historically worked against Black Americans. Clinicians should feel invited to examine how the standard practices they learned may not always be suitable for Black American, how they can modify their methods to suit Black Americans, and how their own behavior may perpetuate anti- Black racism in mental health care. It can also invite African Americans to investigate how history has impacted the mental health of them and their families and invite all members of the population to investigate how their behaviors perpetuate anti-Black racism.

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